

NextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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1 Executive summary

Progress in earth system modelling does not automatically translate into better decisions and policies. For better informed decisions this new data needs to be transformed into useful information and integrated into knowledge, requiring collaboration between scientists and stakeholders. We call this type of collaboration knowledge coproduction. To make it successful, coproduction should include a lasting and iterative process of communication, exchange of ideas and collaboration.

The key platform for knowledge sharing and new knowledge coproduction in NextGEMS are Hackathons. At these events, scientists provide data from the model for participants to test. A guiding inspiration for the hackathons is solving real-world challenge problems, formulated and explored with stakeholders. Another avenue for knowledge coproduction is through development of storylines, such as the storylines of Fisheries and Renewable energy.

To share information, attract and motivate stakeholders, the coproduction process relies on effective and timely communication. The NextGEMS coproduction plan is hence closely aligned with the project communication and dissemination plan.

2 Conclusion & Results

(see executive summary above)

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Implement, monitor and adjust an effective strategy for NextGEMS co-production, communication & dissemination and video presence (O3)	yes
Connect model development and application communities and integrate potential users into the coproduction activities (coproduction process) (O3)	yes
Develop novel communication and dissemination forms to maximize the visibility and usability of the project and its results to target audiences (communication and dissemination) (O3)	yes
Provide technical and policy briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results (policy dissemination) (O3)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable: The NextGEMS coproduction plan

This report explains what is meant by coproduction in NextGEMS and how it is conducted, defining *who* participates in the coproduction process, *how* and *where* the process will take place and *what* will be the result of the coproduction process.

4.1 Knowledge coproduction in earth-system sciences and services

Earth-system and climate services support the incorporation of science-based data and information into planning, policy and practice (Hewitt et al. 2012 [5]; Vaughan and Dessai, 2014 [14]). Moving away from traditional approaches focused primarily on technical advances in earth sciences and their development in isolation to an inclusive transdisciplinary exercise, we need to acknowledge the shift of the focus from earth-system information to processes of coproduction that include building relationships and trust between scientists and users of this information (Daly, 2021 [3]). “Only with such process-oriented, demand-driven and rigorously evaluated approaches will climate services be made useful, useable and used.” (Findlater et al. 2021 [4]). Initiatives aspiring to achieve better informed earth-system governance thus acknowledge the need for greater connectedness to stakeholders’ needs by integrating participatory activities – commonly labelled as user engagement – into the earth-system development agenda (Bojovic et al. 2021 [1]; Bruno Soares and Buontempo, 2019 [2]; Swart et al. 2017 [12]).

We consider here the coproduction process as a process of three incremental phases: engagement, involvement and empowerment (Bojovic et al., 2021 [1]). Engagement is about raising awareness of NextGEMS activities and scientific progress. This phase strongly relies on communication activities (for more details see D10.2 NextGEMS communication and dissemination plan). In the involvement phase, scientists exchange knowledge with stakeholders and explore together real-world problems. Stakeholders are involved through interactive group activities, like meetings, workshops and interviews. Finally, the third phase, empowerment, is the joint creation of new knowledge. It is a transdisciplinary process in which scientific knowledge is combined with domain and sectoral knowledge that stakeholders bring to the process. This requires a genuine knowledge exchange to coproduce new, co-owned knowledge. In this process, stakeholders provide the project with an external perspective, domain knowledge and feedback, ensuring that the products generated are accepted and tailored to user needs, and maximizing their relevance and usability. This equal exchange, through building new knowledge, skills, and partnerships, allows for empowerment of both scientists and stakeholders. Although the project started with awareness raising through communication, the three levels of interaction will continue in parallel, enforcing each other.

The NextGEMS Coproduction Plan is hence developed in parallel to the Communication and Exploitation Plan. Communication and dissemination enable the spread of new ideas and achievements in the project that can serve as motivation for new stakeholders, some of whom would participate in the more profound process of coproduction. The coproduction plan will advance throughout the project, reaching more diverse audiences as the project progresses.

4.2 NextGEMS stakeholders (the *who*)

To reach the genuine knowledge coproduction, we need to start with communication, then to exchange knowledge and finally to co-develop new knowledge with stakeholders. This requires establishing the stakeholder community early in the project and supporting its growth throughout the project, both in scope and in size. NextGEMS conducted stakeholder mapping at the project preparation phase, organizing stakeholders in six key groups (Fig. 1).

NextGEMS stakeholder groups:

1. Scientists: earth science community and wider scientific community;
2. Users: users from renewable energy and fisheries;
3. Broader user community: users from other sectors and domains, including climate services and met offices;
4. Technologists: HPC technologists and high-capacity data experts;
5. Policy-makers: policy and decision makers;
6. Public and media: general public, including local communities from West Africa, and journalists.

Figure 1: NextGEMS stakeholder groups

NextGEMS will apply different engagement approaches for different stakeholders. The six stakeholder groups are generally organised in the NextGEMS *near* and *far* field.

NextGEMS near-field stakeholder groups are: “Users”, “Technologists” and the “Earth-system Science Community”. By near-field, we understand that these stakeholder groups will be part of the most intense forms of exchange, by being directly involved in knowledge coproduction. For example, **users** will be involved in the definition of challenge problems. The Societal Challenge Problems will be guiding the work in hackathons (see section 4.3.1). Presently, the NextGEMS User community involves IBERDROLA, a multi-national Spanish utility company, the DTU (Technical University of Denmark) and VESTAS Wind Systems to explore renewable (solar and wind) energy applications. Another important member of the user group is the Senegalese Institute for Agricultural Research (ISRA) which will help the project to assess how mesoscale ocean variability affects the fisheries practice and potentially food security in the Senegal-Mauritanian up-welling area (North West Africa).

Technologists, particularly as Europe prepares for its first exascale machine, will follow the project’s computational intensity, data management, post-processing, and analysis environments. They will participate in NextGEMS *technology scrums* (see next section 4.3) to help better understand workflow bottlenecks and how the value chain can be extended to seamlessly link to Machine Learning workflows. NextGEMS involves leaders and close contacts to many of the most important Earth-system related information technology projects, such as the ECMWF Scalability program and the Centre of Excellence in High Performance Computing, Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Computing for Weather and Climate formally collaborating with hardware vendors like Atos and NVIDIA. Other connections that project scientists have with the ongoing initiatives and projects will further support close links with Technologists, e.g., Horizon 2020 projects such as ESCAPE-2 and ESIWACE2, national or bi-national projects such as ENIAC (CH/DE), EXCLAIM (CH) and DYAMOND (DE/JP), and WarmWorld (DE). Finally, strong ties to computing centres (e.g., BSC, DKRZ, CSCS in Switzerland and the Jülich Supercomputing Center) will further facilitate contact with and involvement of technologists. NextGEMS will coordinate *technology scrums* as cluster activities with the other projects to strengthen dissemination.

Scientists from the Earthy-system community will be regular participants at NextGEMS hackathons, as demonstrated at the first Hackathon held in October 2021. These stakeholders will work side by side with project scientists to analyse and test immediate model outputs. Scrutinising the physical plausibility of the model outputs, scientists will also help assess reliability and applicability of this new data. This open data and analysis framework is what makes NextGEMS pioneering the new approach to knowledge coproduction in the Earth-system community.

Throughout the course of the project, the near-field stakeholder group will be expanded. We expect to broaden the group of scientists and users who participate in hackathons, as well as to enlarge the group of technologists participating in project technology scrums. For instance, the rapidly growing Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence community is providing an interdisciplinary mix of technologists and users who might be interested to access and exploit the unprecedented data produced in NextGEMS.

Eventually, these knowledge-building events might attract a broader stakeholder community and bring on board new users of NextGEMS knowledge. In the second phase of the project, as the Storm-Resolving Earth-system Models (SR-ESMs) are extended to include a wider range of Earth-system processes and production simulations become available, “new” users, i.e., possessors of different specialist knowledge, will be sought to help define new Challenge Problems to, e.g., assess links between hydro-weather and the carbon cycle, or natural hazards.

The NextGEMS interaction with other stakeholder groups is described in detail in D10.2 NextGEMS Communication and Dissemination Plan.

4.3 Coproduction of knowledge with stakeholders (the *how* and *where*)

Analysing SR-ESMs is at least as challenging as running them, and will be a major task of the NextGEMS community across all phases of the project. The key arena for knowledge coproduction will thus be hackathons and technology scrums. Hackathons and technology scrums will help understand how to effectively work with the vast amount of data NextGEMS will produce, at the same time supporting sharing of this expertise to empower others to make use of it. Hackathons proved (e.g., in previous projects such as DYAMOND) to be an effective way to share expertise, to identify and resolve problems, and to build the human bandwidth required to make a new, usable and used knowledge. Another important avenue for knowledge coproduction with the user group is the development of case studies and storylines.

4.3.1 Hackathons

Hackathons are time-constrained group events for working on predefined challenges to create solutions or innovative applications (Juraschek et al., 2020 [6]). Hackathons originate from the world of software engineering (Pogačar and Žižek, 2016 [10]), but increasingly hackathons and hackathon-like events are being used in other fields, such as climate science, to stimulate creativity in problem solving and enable coproduction of new, shared knowledge (Bojovic et al., 2021 [1]). Hackathons bring the users to the information source avoiding, often criticized in earth-system services, knowledge translation and transfer, and putting emphasis on the coproduction process.

In NextGEMS, we approach hackathons as communal exploration, analysis and development activities – all various forms of “hacking”, that will help us co-develop new, shared knowledge. Hackathons will build on experiences gained from the DYAMOND initiative, which enabled the project to involve a large international community in the analysis of the model output. Hackathons also have the advantage that, when necessary, they can be readily adapted to a virtual environment, or organised as hybrid events, as tested in the NextGEMS first hackathon.

NextGEMS Hackathons are four-to-six-day events involving 40-100 participants working in groups to perform common analyses. They involve people sitting together at tables, or virtually, working with laptops to analyse model outputs. Server-side processing, which keeps the data at the modelling centres and allows users to interact with it using web-based scripting environments (Jupyter Notebooks), makes such activities possible. NextGEMS hackathons will also include team building activities, presentations or breakout sessions to share and discuss evolving results. In parallel to “hacking” activities, we will also host short training exercises, for instance in Science Communication and video recording. With a roughly eight-month frequency, NextGEMS hackathons will also encompass other project meetings, including the General Assembly.

Hackathons will address both model development and knowledge coproduction. Each science theme will organize two hackathons, one each in Phase 1 and 2. Model-development objectives to be addressed in the Phase 1 hackathons will revolve around fine-tuning and preparing the SR-ESMs for the production runs. The user community will, in collaboration with NextGEMS scientists, co-explore and co-design *Societal Challenge Problems* in both Phase 1 and 2 Hackathons.

Hackathon organisers have the task to motivate external participation, seeking links with local institutions, such as universities or renewable energy companies. In addition, by organizing Hackathons in countries without a strong

Name	Location	(estimated) dates
Cycle 1 Hackathon	Berlin	19.10. - 22.10.2021
Cycle 2 Hackathon	Vienna	28.06. - 02.07.2022
Cycle 3 Hackathon	Bucharest or Dublin	Feb - May 2023
Application Hackathon 1	Bucharest or Dublin	winter 2023/2024
Application Hackathon 2	not yet decided	autumn 2024
Application Hackathon 3	not yet decided	spring/ summer 2025

Table 3: The list of hackathons

Earth-system modelling tradition (e.g., Romania, Austria, Ireland) and by providing project funding for external participants, NextGEMS will diversify the community involved in knowledge coproduction.

The first NextGEMS hackathon, held in October 2021 in Berlin, was an excellent opportunity to put into practice the project hackathon plan, test the hybrid event format, and learn what works well and what can be improved further. The participants' wish list for improvements helped collect and organise suggestions for changes in the future. Besides technical and data-oriented suggestions, an interesting proposal was to organise tutorials at the first, optional day, of the next hackathon, as well as to have more outdoor activities that give room for networking, the latter being especially important for early career scientists.

All project principal investigators (PIs) participated in the first hackathon. The first hackathon helped familiarise the PIs with the workflow, contribute to team building, and increased PI's identification with the project. The side-event at the first hackathon was devoted to video recording. In these videos, the project coordinators presented the overall project idea, ambition, and plan. The managers presented some practical aspects of the project, while the theme leads gave an overview of the idea and work planned in each of the four research themes. Latest Thinking recorded the videos in a professional setting. Since video will be the key communication approach in NextGEMS, these first project videos will help us learn what works and what does not work in science communication videos and motivate the preparation of similar, but self-produced videos by project scientists.

A specific type of hackathons, so-called **technology scrums**, will target technologists. Technology scrums will be smaller and more informal than NextGEMS Hackathons, and they will involve members of the modelling groups in addition to the NextGEMS technologists, and selected PIs from the four thematic areas. These will be two-to-three-day events and may often be held virtually.

4.3.2 Storylines

A storyline provides unity to separate discursive components of a physical and social phenomenon, combining them into a coherent whole. Storylines can help study the boundaries of plausibility, enabling exploration of multiple plausible futures. NextGEMS will combine "physical climate storylines" that present self-consistent unfolding of plausible future events or pathways (Shepherd et al., 2018 [11]) with "narrative driven storylines". Building on the physical climate storylines and through collaboration with users, the project will integrate climate information with socio-economic and environmental information. This will expand the scope of issues covered by climate information and improve its integration into social and cultural life, which can help users imagine and visualise the futures but also imagine where society wants to go (Pereira, 2021 [9]). This approach will allow us to move from a static provision of future climate information to a dynamic exercise, showing events and processes that evolve over time and that account for policy response and societal transformation (Krauß, 2020 [7]). The work on storylines will be done in close collaboration between project scientists and users from renewable energy and fisheries through the development of two case studies: Renewable energy in the changing world and Fisheries and food security in Western Africa.

4.4 The expected output of the coproduction process (the *what*)

4.4.1 Hackathons

The coproduction component of the Hackathons will be organised by the Storms&Society theme (S&S) jointly with the respective science theme leads. The aim is to bring together scientists, engineers, communication specialists, and users already in the model development phase using the Societal Challenge Problems. Hackathon themes will articulate challenge problems related to: renewable energy, involving utilities, users and the modelling community; fisheries; and risk and hazard assessment. As an example, the Storms&Radiation theme will organize a NextGEMS Hackathon with its knowledge coproduction focus on renewable energy. Here NextGEMS scientists working with experts from the wind-energy industry will outline a problem that can be addressed with NextGEMS output. External participants will work in teams to solve the problem, with coordination provided by members of the lead science themes. The challenge problem will help guide the development of the SR-ESMs, and their associated workflows, in ways that better expose their information content to application communities. Stakeholders in solar and wind energy, with whom a bi-directional process is initiated through the knowledge coproduction activities in the development phase, will later be involved in a follow-up hackathon, further exploring the online diagnostics implemented into the SR-ESMs. The production runs will be exploited to address the challenging question of how renewable energy production is affected by the changing weather conditions following climate change. This may also include investigation of frequency and intensity of extreme events in terms of energy production, for instance high pressure winter conditions under which both wind and solar energy production will be low on a large scale. To support these efforts, key sectors have been involved in the project from the beginning. In these terms, IBERDROLA is a NextGEMS consortium member. They will develop methods of assessing renewable energy production – with an initial focus on cloud and aerosol effects on solar energy – directly from SR-ESM simulations; and experts from the DTU (Technical University of Denmark) and VESTAS Wind Systems will collaborate with NextGEMS to explore wind energy applications.

The Storms&Ocean theme will co-organise, together with S&S, a hackathon that will bring the community together to address the challenging question of whether it is important to resolve meso- and sub-mesoscales in the oceanic component of ESMs when assessing climate change. As an example, one topic could be the passive uptake of Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), heat and anthropogenic carbon by the ocean in the multi-decadal NextGEMS simulations, estimated from the passive tracers. The passive uptake of CFCs, heat and anthropogenic carbon is very sensitive to water mass formation and vertical mixing, and thus, it should be sensitive to mesoscale and sub-mesoscale processes. This Challenge Problem will be co-defined and co-explored with the two project partners with the domain knowledge: IRD and ISPR. These coproduction activities around fisheries will help assess how mesoscale ocean variability affects the small pelagic fish dynamics as well as macro-zooplanktonic abundance in the Senegalo-Mauritanian upwelling area (North West Africa).

Finally, collaboration between the Storms&Land and S&S will result in a hazard hackathon. This hackathon will bring the science and user communities together in the theme of natural hazards. The challenge of the hackathon will be to convert the output of SR-ESMs into detailed and meaningful maps that provide stakeholders outside of the science community means of communicating risks of natural hazards. The initial focus will be on fires, heat waves, and extreme precipitation, but further hazards will be added based on the interests of participants of the hackathon.

4.4.2 Case studies and storylines

By having the two key users as equal partners in the project, IBERDROLA and ISRA, NextGEMS addresses the issues of lack of partnership or power inequality in knowledge coproduction processes (Norstrom et al., 2020 [8]; Turnhout et al., 2020 [13]). The pilot studies developed with users will be presented in the form of storylines (D10.7 Storyline on Fishery pilot study and D10.8 Storyline of Renewable Energy pilot study). The users involved in coproduction will play the role of dissemination ambassadors in their fields, facilitating the link and sharing of coproduced knowledge to other stakeholders, as well as related socio-economic sectors and thus increasing the NextGEMS user community.

Finally, the project will organise meetings, workshops and side-events to enlarge the stakeholder community and involve further potential users. This will include: meetings with the user and technologists community during the hackathons, workshops with stakeholders from Western Africa to address particular issues relevant for this region, webinars for the broader stakeholder community, and side-events at key scientific conferences, such as EGU, AGU, ECCA, Adaptation Futures, Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) events. At some of these events we will host storyline workshops, where the storylines will be presented during their development process and the feedback

Figure 2: Illustration of interaction intensity during the first Hackathon. The circles are the nodes – the hackathon participants – and their size indicates the degree centrality: the number of connections a person has. The nodes are distributed in groups based on the working theme (radiation, surface fluxes, etc.) and the colour of the node indicates the institutional affiliation. Finally, the labels are coloured in green if the node was also a theme leader or red else. This is a directed graph, signaled by the direction of the arrows.

collected.

4.4.3 Assessing the coproduction process in hackathons

Besides the new earth-system knowledge and its application in the targeted fields, such as renewable energy and fisheries, another important output of NextGEMS is the process of coproduction itself. This process-focused approach prioritizes engagement, coproduction, use and evaluation of new knowledge (Bojovic et al., 2021 [1]; Findlater et al., 2021 [4]). To examine and follow this process, we will apply Social Network Analysis (SNA). SNA investigates interaction patterns and network structures established between actors. Hackathon participants will fill in a short survey after each event in which they will assess their relationship with other hackathon participants, indicating the intensity and the novelty of this link. We will then analyse how the network structure evolves throughout the project, with each consecutive hackathon. We will in particular monitor interactions between the group leads and other participants, between participants from different groups, interactions between NextGEMS members from different themes, or interactions between NextGEMS-ers and other hackathon participants, to name some of these interactions that can be captured through SNA. As an example, Figure 2 depicts some of the interactions captured at the first NextGEMS hackathons.

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6 Dissemination and uptake

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not relevant.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

There is a link with D10.2, the NextGEMS Communication and Dissemination Plan.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon, 19.10. - 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - Activity: NextCalendArt 2022

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.